

Young Researchers in Archaeometry

YRA Workshop 2024

October 15–18, 2024

Nicosia, Cyprus

Abstract Book

Organisers:

Anna Karligkioti
Kyriaki Tsirtsis
Chase Minos
Thomas Rose

Hosted at

© 2024 The Authors.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Supported by

ΤΜΗΜΑ ΑΡΧΑΙΟΤΗΤΩΝ
DEPARTMENT OF ANTIQUITIES
ΚΥΠΡΟΥ | CYPRUS

We thank our sponsors

Programme

All times are given in Eastern European Summer Time (UTC+3).

Lecture halls:

- Fresnel – John Ioannides Auditorium (all sessions)
- Mouskos Auditorium (keynote lecture and movie screening on Wednesday, 16th of October)

Presentations will be streamed on [Zoom](#)

(<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/88340660574> | Meeting ID: 883 4066 0574 | Passcode: 081518)

Tuesday, 15 October

20:00 Ice breaker (self-paid) at Charátsi, Eptanisou, Nicosia 1016

Wednesday, 16 October

09:00 – 09:30 Registration

09:30 – 09:50 Welcome

Session 1: Cultural heritage/non-invasive methods

09:50 – 10:10 Archaeometric analysis of the inks in two 15th century Greek paper manuscripts: a preliminary comparative study
Katerina Grigoriadou

10:10 – 10:30 Non-invasive material analysis of Egyptian Shabtis by XRF, Raman spectroscopy and CT Scanning
Stelios Aspiotis, Olivier Bonnerot, Samaneh Ehteram, Leah Mascia

10:30 – 10:50 Multi-analytical investigation on the carved oriental lacquerwares
Shang-ying Liu, Patrizia Tomasin, Luca Nodari, Marta Boscolo Marchi, Alfonso Zoleo

10:50 – 11:10 *Coffee break*

11:10 – 11:30 Revealing Hidden Histories: Using High-Resolution Portable Computed Tomography for Closed Cuneiform Tablets
Samaneh Ehteram

- 11:30 – 11:50 3D Visualization and Digital Recording of Sculptures through Photogrammetry: An Iconometric Examination of the Hoysala Sculptures
Poorva Salvi
- 11:50 – 12:10 Shallow Offshore Archaeological Prospection in Ancient Olous, Crete
Angelos Plageras, Dimitrios Oikonomou, Nikos Papadopoulos
- 12:10 – 12:30 Breaking into the “Black Box”: The contribution of ethnographic work in decoding Late Cypriot household structures
Chara Theotokatou
- 12:30 – 12:50 The Master, PhD, training Programs offered by The Cyprus Institute
Head of the Graduate School, Cyprus Institute
- 12:50 – 14:00 *Lunch break*

Session 2: Ceramics, part 1

- 14:00 – 14:20 Clay for pots. Raw Material Determination of Sântana “Cetatea Veche” Ceramics and Determination of Firing Methods in Late Bronze Age
Alexandra Stache, Ágnes Gál, Florin Gogâltan
- 14:20 – 14:40 Disclosing Production Process by the Archaeometric Analysis of Bronze to Iron Age Ceramic Jars from Qatna (Central Syria)
Bianca Costi Farias, Lara Maritan, Claudio Mazzoli, Marco Iamoni, Daniele Morandi

Session 3: Environmental Archaeology and Bioarchaeology

- 14:40 – 15:10 Ongoing Archaeobotanical Research in Mycenaean Iklaina, Messenia, Greece
Symeon Gkinoudis, Evi Margaritis
- 15:10 – 15:30 Phytolith analysis for the investigation of plant exploitation in Bronze Age Cyprus
Georgia Kasapidou
- 15:30 – 15:50 Fuelling Ancient Idalion: Charcoal Analysis and Insights into 1st Millennium BCE Cyprus
Panagiotis Koullouros
- 15:50 – 16:30 *Coffee break* (room: Mouskos)
- 16:30 – 16:35 Welcome address by the *President of the Cyprus Institute*
- 16:35 – 17:15 Keynote: Domesticity, craft production and ritual: Changing patterns of human life in the 3rd millennium BCE Aegean (room: Mouskos)
Assoc. Prof. Evi Margaritis, Dr. Michael Boyd (The Cyprus Institute), Colin A. Renfrew (University of Cambridge)

17:30 – 19:00 Screening of the movie: Buried Secrets of Keros (room: Mouskos)
National Geographic, UK ([Watch the official trailer on Youtube](#))

Thursday, 17 October

Session 4: Ceramics, part 2

- 09:00 – 09:20 Fragments of the Past from Zeytinli Bahçe Höyük: Deciphering Cultural and Technological Interactions from the Late Chalcolithic to the Early Bronze Age through Ceramic Petrography
Rosa Crocco
- 09:20 – 09:40 Paint It, Red: A Technological and Compositional Study of Classical Pottery from Nea Paphos, Cyprus
Geneviève Lascombes, Edyta Marzec, Lara Maritan
- 09:40 – 10:00 The Clay of a Gateway Community In Cyprus – Domestic Pottery from Soli
Marie-Louise Jahn Hansen
- 10:00 – 10:20 Late Hellenistic braziers from Delos; provenance study and characterisation of 'Cycladic' type
Athena Konstandara, Edyta Marzec
- 10:20 – 10:40 Influence of decantation on Mediterranean clay: An experimental archaeological approach
Vania Filippou, Lara Maritan, Virginie Renson, Daria Pasqual, Silvia Cattò, Eleni Nodarou, Emma Cantisani, Maria Dikomitou Eliadou, Zomenia Zomeni
- 10:40 – 11:00 *Coffee break*
- 11:00 – 11:20 Envisioning Pre-Colombian Regional Trade Patterns Through Elemental Analysis of Archaeological Ceramics from Western Panama
Carly Pope, Scott Palumbo, Laure Dussubieux
- 11:20 – 11:40 μ -LIBS imaging as spatially-resolved and quantitative characterization method for pottery
Nicolas Herreyre, Valérie Merle, Anne Schmitt, Christine Oberlin, Clothilde Comby-Zebino, Vincent Motto-Ros
- 11:40 – 12:00 Knowledge exchange in pottery production in Neolithic Northwest China: a petrographic study and the resulting development of a digital tool for petrographic image analysis in archaeology
Evgenia Dammer
- 12:00 – 12:20 Mineralogical and Petrographic Study of Tuyères from Pongsolo (Lekie, Central Cameroon)
Epossi Ntah Zoila Luz-Kroll, Thomas Rose

- 12:20 – 13:20 *Lunch break*
- 13:20 – 15:40 *Session 5: Posters*
- 15:40 – 16:00 *Coffee break*
- 16:00 – 18:00 Lab tour
- 18:00 – 19:00 Keynote: The prehistoric roots of the Mediterranean diet
Dr. Juan José García-Granero (Spanish National Research Council, Spain)
Join the live stream on YouTube: <https://youtube.com/live/BMyuaxiWt8>
- 19:00 – 20:00 *Reception sponsored by the Spanish Embassy*
- 20:30 Dinner at *Fisa & Masa, Ledras 55, Nicosia 1011*
Traditional Tavern with Cypriot mezes and live music

Friday, 18 October

Session 6: Metallurgy, part 1

- 9:00 – 9:30 Keynote: The Future of Archaeological Science
Prof. Thilo Rehren (*The Cyprus Institute*)
- 09:30 – 09:50 The elemental composition of bog ores in Masovia (Poland) and its affect on the reconstruction of the smelting process
Antonina Bełtowska-Bednarkiewicz
- 09:50 – 10:10 Bronze Production in Archaic and Classical Northern Greece: A Archaeometric Approach to the Study of Bronze Objects from Ancient Argilos
Justine Lefebvre
- 10:10 – 10:40 *Coffee break*
- 10:40 – 11:00 Silver-lead and copper production on Early Bronze Age southern Sifnos: an overview
Magda Giannakopoulou
- 11:00 – 11:20 TerraLID: Further steps towards a new ecosystem for lead isotope data in archaeology
Thomas Rose, Tim Greifelt, Katrin J. Westner, Annette Hornschuch, Yiu-Kang Hsu, Helge Wiethoff, Sabine Klein
- 11:20 – 11:40 Metalworking materials and practices from Late Antique Rome
Giulia Bison, Jose Cristobal Carvajal Lopez

Session 7: Metallurgy, part 2 and Archaeomaterials

- 11:40 – 12:00 Commercial High Alumina Crucibles for Melting Alkali and Alkaline Earth Metal Salt Mixtures to Replicate Ancient Glass Production
Marcel Frenken, Meghna Desai, Thilo Rehren
- 12:00 – 12:20 The Interaction between Persian Gulf and Indian Peninsula during the middle-late Islamic Period: Compositional Evidence for the High-Alumina Glass Bangles Discovered from Coastal Sites of Qatar and U.A.E.
Qian Cheng, Thilo Rehren, Robert Andrew Carter, Xueyan Zhang
- 12:20 – 12:40 Identifying a Peloponnesian palette: pigment analysis of domestic architecture from Stymphalos
Alice Clinch
- 12:40 – 13:00 The “production” of Minoan red serpentinite
Killian Regnier
- 13:00 – 13:20 Awards ceremony and group photo
- 13:20 – 14:30 *Lunch break*
- 14:30 – 15:00 Keynote: Ritual Faunal Deposits in Prehistoric Sanctuaries: Zooarchaeological Insights from the Gymnesic Islands (Western Mediterranean)
Dr. Alejandro Valenzuela Oliver (Mediterranean Institute for Advanced Studies (UIB-CSIC), Spain)
- 15:00 – 15:10 Closing/Final remarks
- 15:30 Bus transfer from the Cyprus Institute to Nicosia city centre
- 17:00 – 19.30 Experimental pyre: Food for the Gods Sacrificial Pyres in the Archaeological Record and guided tours in the Lendron Archaeological Local Museum

Saturday, 19 October

Morning Visit of the Cyprus Museum (free admission)

Posters

- Trace element influence on phytolith dissolution and preservation: Investigating the role of strontium and barium
Nafsika C. Andriopoulou, Georgios E. Christidis
- Deciphering Past Coastal Environments: Beachrock Characterisation and Luminescence Dating in SE Lasithi, Crete, Greece
Nafsika C. Andriopoulou, Georgios C. Polymeris, Konstantinos C. Stamoulis, Michael Schöbel, Georgios E. Christidis, Stefanos Papadakis, Anna Novikova, Nikos Papadopoulos
- A look upon chalcolithic pottery technology through the petrographic analysis of a batch from North of Danube
Mădălina Dimache, Cristian-Eduard Ștefan
- Furthering our understanding of the sources of the metal of Roman denarii – A multi-isotope and elemental analysis approach
Tim Greifelt, Sabine Klein, David Wigg-Wolf
- An application of XRF spectroscopy to heritage science - the case study of ancient roman building materials from Lebanon
Marcin Sokołowski
- Experimental clay processing and archaeometric analysis to determine the provenance of fine-ware ceramics from the Early Middle Ages in north-western Tuscany (Italy): preliminary results
Irene Strufaldi, Sara Longo
- The RETS Project - Revealing the Senne. A hidden landmark in the historical center of Brussels, Belgium
Dries Vergouwen, Ann Degraeve, Marc Meganck, Ralf Vandam, Yannick Devos

Archaeometric analysis of the inks in two 15th century Greek paper manuscripts: a preliminary comparative study

Katerina Grigoriadou^{1*}

¹ University of Hamburg, Centre for the Study of Manuscript Cultures (CSMC) - Cluster of Excellence "Understanding Written Artefacts", Hamburg, Germany

* aikaterini.grigoriadou@uni-hamburg.de

Keywords: ink analysis, XRF, Visible Spectroscopy, FTIR, Greek manuscripts, Ioannes Rhosos, 15th century

Voss. Gr. Q. 25 (University Library of Leiden) and Cod. in scrin. 145 (State and University Library of Hamburg), are two paper codices, probably produced in Venice in the late 15th century C.E. (ca. 1480-1498). Despite the absence of colophons in the manuscripts, their distinct palaeographical characteristics strongly suggest that they were penned by the hand of Ioannes Rhosos, a renowned professional calligrapher from the Greek island of Crete, who was copying manuscripts for prominent commissioners in Italy during the second half of the 15th century. This paper will a) present the preliminary results of the multi-analytical examination of the black and red inks, that were used by Rhosos in the copying of the two manuscripts and b) provide an initial comparison of the types and compositions of these inks between the two codices. The in-depth analysis and comparison of the inks of the two case studies contribute to the understanding of the types of inks produced and used in the Veneto region by the late 15th century. Equally important, the results obtained in this research constitute a first step towards profiling the working process of a Renaissance important calligrapher in terms of the writing substances he employed. The analysis for this study was performed using non-invasive and non-destructive analytical techniques, such as Ultraviolet (UV) and near-infrared (NIR) reflectography, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), Visible (VIS) spectroscopy and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR).

Non-invasive material analysis of Egyptian Shabtis by XRF, Raman spectroscopy and CT Scanning

Stelios Aspiotis^{1,2*}, Samaneh Ehteram¹, Leah Mascia¹

¹ Cluster of Excellence “Understanding Written Artefacts”, Universität Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany

² Department of Earth System Sciences, Universität Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany

* stylianos.aspiotis@uni-hamburg.de

Keywords: Shabtis, CT-scanning, XRF, Raman spectroscopy

In ancient Egyptian culture, shabtis were sets of figurines in the form of mummies made of faience, stone, or wood traditionally deposited inside tombs. According to the Pharaonic funerary beliefs, these figurines acted as magical substitutes for the deceased when the gods called him (or her) to undertake menial tasks in the afterlife. Studying the production process of faience shabtis in addition to their design and engraved inscriptions can provide valuable information. The mineral phase characterization of shabtis kept in museum collections has relied on traditional gemological methods based on visual observations, which are rather inconclusive or too generic and are hindered from the glazed surface of many shabtis. The uniqueness and historical value of these cultural-heritage objects make sampling prohibitive, leading to the growing popularity of non-destructive and non-invasive analytical techniques that are sensitive to both chemistry and crystal structure. Raman spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy and computed tomography (CT) scanning are such non-destructive analytical methods that have been successfully applied for the determination of structure, elemental composition, firing conditions and hidden subsurface structures of painted and enamelled objects. In this study, selected faience shabtis from the collection of the Museum für Kunst und Gewerbe Hamburg (MKG) were studied by XRF, Raman spectroscopy, and CT Scanning. We show that the combination of these techniques can (i) determine the major, minor, and trace element composition within each mineral phase, (ii) identify the glazing techniques used to produce shabtis, and (iii) reveal structural characteristics of the glaze and subsurface layers.

Multi-analytical investigation on the carved oriental lacquerwares

Shang-ying Liu^{1*}, Patrizia Tomasin², Luca Nodari², Marta Boscolo Marchi³, Alfonso Zoleo⁴

¹ Department of Cultural Heritage: Archaeology and History of Art, Cinema and Music/Archaeological Sciences/Applied sciences to cultural heritage materials and sites, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

² The National Research Council, Padova, Italy

³ Museo d'Arte orientale, Venice, Italy ⁴ Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

* shangyingliu631@gmail.com

Keywords: oriental lacquer, urushi, historical research, multiple scientific analysis, Oriental Art Museum of Venice, material study, non-invasive methods, FORS, IR, Raman, SEM, Py-GC-MS, EPR

This research project aims to explore the origins and restoration of four lacquerwares at the Oriental Art Museum of Venice using both historical research and multi-scientific methods. The artifacts include three red carved lacquer pieces and one painted lacquer piece, some of which are deteriorating and cracking. Scientific tests will help verify their provenance (China or Japan), as existing literature lacks detailed records. The study combines historical research and materials science to provide comprehensive information for future restoration. Historical research will examine the museum's collection history and interpret the iconography, hypothesizing possible techniques mentioned in ancient texts. Non-invasive tests using a Digital Microscope, Fiber Optic Reflectance Spectroscopy (FORS), Infrared External Reflection Module, and Raman Spectroscopy will analyze pigments and materials. Micro-samples will be analyzed using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), μ -FTIR Spectroscopy, and Pyrolysis-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) to identify components, additives, and possibly the origin. Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) will study the degradation process. The study aims to enhance the understanding of Asian lacquerware's craftsmanship and provenance and provide insights into using various scientific instruments for lacquerware analysis, supporting future restoration and preservation efforts.

Revealing hidden histories: Using high-resolution portable computed tomography for closed Cuneiform Tablets

Samaneh Ehteram^{1,2*}

¹ Cluster of Excellence “Understanding Written Artefacts”, Universität Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany

² Center of X-ray and Nano Science CXNS, Deutsches Elektronen Synchrotron (DESY), Hamburg, Germany

* samaneh.ehteram@desy.de

Keywords: portable CT scanner, enveloped cuneiform tablets, non-destructive technique, Louvre Museum

Cuneiform represents the earliest form of writing developed by the Sumerians in Mesopotamia in the 2nd half of the 4th millennium BCE. From the middle of the 3rd millennium BCE, people wrote legal documents and sent many letters. To protect the tablets and ensure confidentiality, tablets were encased in clay envelopes. These envelopes featured the names of the sender, the seal imprint using cylinder seals, and the name(s) of the addressee(s). Reading the message required breaking the envelope, however, some letters never reached their recipient and remained within their clay envelopes for thousands of years. The study of enveloped clay tablets serves as an important reminder that unopened heritage artifacts conceal the narratives of their past within both their textual contents and structural integrity. As such, this research aims to explore the application of non-destructive techniques on enveloped clay tablets. In this contribution we present our efforts in developing a portable high-resolution X-ray tomographic scanner, designed in collaboration with the cluster of excellence at Universität Hamburg ‘Understanding Written Artifacts’ and Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron. The X-ray scanner can be assembled and dismantled for use in museums and collections. This newly developed device was recently used for the very first time at the Louvre Museum, yielding excellent tomographic data on twelve contracts and administrative texts from the end of the 3rd and the beginning of the 2nd millennium BCE. This innovative system facilitates comprehensive non-destructive measurement of enveloped tablets, covering the entire measurement process from data acquisition to on-site 3D visualization.

3D visualization and digital recording of sculptures through photogrammetry: An iconometric examination of the Hoysala sculptures

Poorva Salvi^{1*}

¹ Archaeological Sciences Centre, Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India

* poorva.salvi@iitgn.ac.in

Keywords: photogrammetry, iconometry, Hoysala sculptures, 3D documentation

Iconometry, in the Indian context, refers to the study of the measurements of the sculptures and was referred to as the Talamana system in the ancient scriptures. This study aims to integrate Photogrammetry into the study of iconometry to improve the documentation of the sculptures and minimise the margin of error that anthropometric tools and manual documentation unintentionally but often record. To fulfil the aforementioned objective, a sample of sculptures from six temples of the Hoysala dynasty (10th c. CE - 13th c. CE) were shortlisted. Extensive fieldwork was conducted to document the sculptures using high-resolution, scaled photography, and the images were further processed in the IIT Gandhinagar's Earth Sciences Department Lab using Agisoft Metashape software's photogrammetric processing. The 3D models of the shortlisted sculptures were generated through the software, and measurements were extracted from those models for further iconometric analysis. This approach could provide accuracy to the measurements of the sculptures with minimal to zero margin of error, which subsequently can be extremely significant while analysing the iconometry of the sculptures.

Shallow offshore archaeological Prospection in ancient Olous, Crete

Angelos Plageras^{1,2*}, Dimitrios Oikonomou¹, Nikos Papadopoulos¹

¹ Lab of Geophysical - Satellite Remote Sensing and Archaeoenvironment, Institute for Mediterranean Studies, Foundation for Research and Technologie Hellas, Rethymnon, Greece

² Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Faculty of Sciences, School of Geology, Dept of Geophysics, Thessaloniki, Greece

* alarbrotz@Gmail.com

Keywords: prospection, marine geophysics, 3D dynamic ERT, cultural heritage

Archaeological prospection in aquatic sites presents unique challenges compared to land surveys. Until recently, most research efforts were focused on adapting instrumentation and processing methods for mapping cultural objects in deep marine environment. However, the implementation of similar methods in ultra-shallow coastal areas poses specific difficulties due to the challenging environmental context. Preserving cultural layers in these areas is crucial due to factors like rising sea levels, coastal erosion and human activity, which may threaten cultural heritage integrity. Thus, the effective documentation of coastal and ultra-shallow sites requires the integration of modified methodological approaches, both in terms of instrumentation and processing algorithms. The sunken city of Ancient Olous, in modern Elounda, Crete, Greece, holds significant archaeological importance, with evidence of inhabitation since the Archaic period. Offshore geophysical prospection utilizing three-dimensional (3-D) Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT) successfully mapped a submerged fortress wall and identified potential archaeological targets buried below the seabed. The results highlight the importance of shallow offshore marine geophysics in archaeological research, offering new tools for coastal zone exploration and integration with land sites underscoring at the same time the importance of this evolving field. By addressing challenges unique to coastal areas, such as dynamic underwater conditions and limited visibility, shallow offshore geophysical prospection can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of maritime archaeology. Further development of the methodological flowcharts and integration into archaeological projects, promises to enhance the study and preservation of submerged cultural heritage worldwide.

Breaking into the “black box”: The contribution of ethnographic work in decoding Late Cypriot household structures

Chara Theotokatou^{1*}

¹ Department of History and Archaeology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece

* xara.th97@gmail.com

Keywords: Cyprus, LBA, households, ethnography

Archaeological research frequently places the remains of domestic environments in the epicenter of discourse, aiming to monitor and comprehend the social organization of past societies. Regarding the Late Bronze Age in Cyprus, though, research usually emphasizes on the elite dwellings and practices. While previous research has made significant progress in investigating the social complexity of the Late Cypriot communities, ongoing research is still far from thoroughly understanding the foundations of these societies. For this reason, a bottom-up approach is needed, focusing on the smallest social units, i.e., households. These structures can only be decoded through an in-depth analysis and interpretation of their functions and behaviors, which can be challenging. Nevertheless, as Wilk highlights, only by tracing these functions, ongoing research can break into the “black box” of households. Ethnographic parallels, especially of pre-industrial societies, are invaluable to this process. Although we cannot directly project the social processes of later communities onto the Late Cypriot period, ethnographic parallels shed light on traditional –and at times forgotten– everyday practices. Therefore, this paper attempts to connect Late Cypriot household practices to the ethnographic record, aiming to provide an in-depth understanding of the activities occurring within Late Cypriot habitation units and, thus, their socioeconomic organization.

Clay for pots: Raw material determination of Sântana “Cetatea Veche” ceramics and determination of firing methods in Late Bronze Age

Alexandra Stache^{1,2*}, Ágnes Gál¹

¹ Department of Geology, Biology and Geology Faculty, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

² Department of Ancient History and Archaeology, History and Philosophy Faculty, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

³ Archaeology, Romanian Academy Institute of Archaeology and Art History, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

* stachealexuta@yahoo.com

Keywords: Late Bronze Age, ceramics, Sântana, provenance studies

The present research aims to determine the relationship between prehistoric people of the Late Bronze Age site in Sântana “Cetatea Veche” (“Old Fortress”) (Arad county, Romania) and the environment through its material culture, respectively ceramics. The question we address is if the community used local clay for the pottery and if so, what kind of pottery technology was required. In order to answer this question, twenty shards were chosen to analyse, each of them having different traits regarding firing technique. The shards were discovered in the defensive ditch of the enclosure I, during the research excavation the took place in 2019 at the mega-fort of Sântana “Cetatea Veche”, situated in the Lower Mureş basin. While analysing the pottery shards, we are using both XRDP and the polarizing microscope methods to define the firing temperatures and the provenance of the raw material. The mineral composition of the ceramic paste will be then compared with the mineral composition of geological formation samples from the area.

Disclosing production process by the archaeometric analysis of Bronze to Iron Age ceramic jars from Qatna (Central Syria)

Bianca Costi Farias^{1*}, Lara Maritan², Claudio Mazzoli², Marco Iamoni³, Daniele Morandi³

¹ Department of Cultural Heritage: Archaeology and History of Art, Cinema and Music, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

² Department of Geosciences, University of Padova, Padova, Italy

³ Department of Humanities and Cultural Heritage, University of Udine, Udine, Italy

* bianca.costifarias@studenti.unipd.it

Keywords: ceramic analysis, ceramic petrography, Bronze Age, Syria

This work presents the current results of the archaeometric study carried out on 121 samples of jars from the site of Qatna (Tell Mishrifeh, central Syria), dated from the early Bronze age to the Iron age. The samples were characterized in terms of mineral composition by X-Ray Powder Diffraction (XRPD), petro-fabric by optical microscopy, chemical composition by X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) and the results were then combined with the typological features (shapes). This diachronic research enabled the identification of a change in the petro-fabric from the Early Bronze Age to the Iron Age, which can be interpreted in terms of modifications in the production recipe, firing, and production techniques of the jars. As the ceramic material here analyzed corresponds to the first in central Syria to be stratigraphically excavated and dated in absolute terms, this provides a significant step into deciphering the history of this important site. This research highlights the possibility of application of archaeometric data to understand the manufacturing techniques and provenance of this ceramic material, while also enabling a reconstruction of circulation patterns of pottery between Bronze and Iron Age Syria.

Ongoing archaeobotanical research in Mycenaean Iklaina, Messenia, Greece

Symeon Gkinoudis^{1*}, Evi Margaritis¹

¹ The Science and Technology in Archaeology and Culture Research Center, The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus

* sginoudis@gmail.com

Keywords: Archaeobotany, macroremains

The contribution of Environmental studies for understanding the nature of the agrarian economy in the Late Bronze Age Aegean has been widely neglected by previous research. Although archaeobotanical remains were recovered from the first excavations at Aegean sites during the late 19th and early 20th centuries, little attention has been paid to their systematic retrieval and study, since previous research was heavily based on the textual Linear B evidence. Today, although essential research steps have been done, unfortunately, many Aegean archaeologists still consider the archaeobotanical remains as a “second line of evidence”. To contribute to this gap in evidence and to answer basic inquiries on the nature of Mycenaean agrarian economy, systematic archaeobotanical sampling has been applied in Iklaina, in Messenia, Greece. Previous research on the site attests uninterrupted habitation from the LH I to LH III periods. The material that is going to be presented has been retrieved from three individual units, Building NE-A, Building P and Building Z, all of which are dated to the palatial period. Basic inquiries that are at the core of this research are the nature of the agrarian economy at the site (diversified and/or specialized farming) and to distinguish patterns of production before and after the incorporation of Iklaina in the administrative network of Pylos.

Phytolith analysis for the investigation of plant exploitation in Bronze Age Cyprus

Georgia Kasapidou^{1*}

¹ The Cyprus Institute

* g.kasapidou@cyi.ac.cy

Keywords: archaeobotany, phytolith analysis

The transition of Middle to Late Bronze Age in Cyprus is a significant turning point for the formation and the gradual emergence of more specialized and complex societies. The archaeological research has put emphasis on the study of metallurgy and the long- distance maritime trade for the investigation of the development of this social complexity while aspects such as agricultural intensification and subsistence practices have been neglected. This also could be the result of the limited recovery of archaeobotanical macro- remains from Cypriot Bronze Age sites due to depositional restrictions. This paper aims to contribute on the current research regarding the agricultural practices and the plant exploitation based on the analysis of phytoliths from two sites, Erimi-Laonin tou Porakou and Erimi-Pitharka. Erimi- Laonin tou Porakou is a Middle Bronze Age site consisted of a habitational area, a textile workshop, circular wall and funerary area. On the other hand, Erimi-Pitharka is a Late Bronze Age site, located in close distance south of Erimi-Laonin tou Porakou, includes a building complex related to storage and industrial activities associated to agricultural production. Phytolith analysis reveals a wide range of plant related practices providing comparative data about the agricultural economy at a regional level diachronically.

Fuelling ancient Idalion: Charcoal analysis and insights into 1st millennium BCE Cyprus

Panagiotis Koullouros^{1*}

¹ The Cyprus Institute

* p.koullouros@cyi.ac.cy

Keywords: charcoal analysis, anthracology, 1st millennium BCE

The site of ancient Idalion lies in the centre of the island of Cyprus around 20km southeast of modern-day Nicosia. The site is of vital importance as it is closely situated to the copper mining zone in the eastern foothills of Troodos mountains, and the fertile valley of the Yialias River. The earliest settlement of the site dates to the 13th to 12th century BCE, while during the excavations conducted by the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus, a Phoenician administrative centre was identified dating to the 4th century BCE. Although, archaeobotanical studies are fundamental in exploring the relationship between communities and the natural environment, bringing forward various characteristics of everyday life in ancient societies, research centring on wood charcoal during the 1st millennium BCE Cyprus have been limited. Thus, this paper seeks to fill this gap by investigating the intricate relations between humans and their natural environment through the application of wood charcoal analysis. This paper also aims to emphasize the key role of archaeobotanical studies in supplementing our understanding of ancient societies by focusing on key aspects such as timber procurement and fuel economy. Simultaneously, it seeks to understand the intricacies of daily life at ancient Idalion.

Paint it, red: A technological and compositional study of classical pottery from Nea Paphos, Cyprus

Geneviève Lascombes^{1*}, Edyta Marzec², Lara Maritan¹

¹ Padua University, Italy ² Fitch Laboratory, British School at Athens

* genevievelascombes@gmail.com

Keywords: ceramic technology, petrography, archaeometry, Classical Cyprus

The topographical and archaeological evidence coming from excavations in Nea Paphos suggests that occupation of the area already began in the Classical times, in other words before the foundation of the city in the late 4th c. BCE. Architectural remains representing this period are scarce, but contexts associated with the pre-urban phase as well as Hellenistic and Roman layers yielded ceramic materials of Classical date. This paper focuses on the Classical tableware pottery retrieved from two excavations in Nea Paphos (Maloutena and the Agora) in order to provide more information on the human activity during the period in question. Samples representing various types of bowls and plates were subjected to mineralogical and elemental analyses. The investigations afforded the reconstruction of the chaîne opératoire and consumption patterns of table wares in south-western Cyprus in the Classical period. The comparison of the studied material with already analyzed Hellenistic table ware from Nea Paphos contributes to the exploration of the local potting tradition as well as how it was impacted by socio-economic and political changes.

The clay of a gateway community in Cyprus: domestic pottery from Soli

Marie-Louise Jahn Hansen^{1,2,3*}

¹ The Saxo Institute, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

² STARC, The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus

³ Medelhavsmuseet, Världskulturmuseerna, Stockholm, Sweden

* mjh@hum.ku.dk

Keywords: petrography, pXRF

This paper sets out to investigate Hellenistic and Roman domestic pottery excavated by the Swedish Cyprus Expedition in the location of Soli, Cyprus, to outline a possible local production of pottery in the near vicinity of the city-state and to examine the connection between the copper-producing areas of Troodos and the northern coastline. Extensive scientific analyses of ceramics found in Soli are essential for the ongoing discussion of a probable local production of ceramics in Soli. The aim is to contribute to the debate of whether a production of domestic pottery took place in the area by studying material found in the actual location. Local production and distribution of such allow for further debate on the social networks and financial role of the city-state of Soli during the Hellenistic and Roman periods. I analysed 50 samples of cooking ware and plain ware pottery by petrography (thin sections) and portable X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (pXRF), and I included five locally produced amphorae of the Mavrovouni and Skouriotissa types from different locations. Moreover, I had access to previously prepared thin sections of similar types of amphorae found in the Lagoudera area of Troodos as comparable material for my study. Before starting the scientific analyses, I established a preliminary typology based on comparable material and macroscopic descriptions of the fabric. The initial registrations indicated locally produced groups of pottery, which did not compare with pottery found in other locations in and outside Cyprus during the same period.

Late Hellenistic braziers from Delos: provenance study and characterisation of “Cycladic” type

Athena Konstandara^{1*}, Edyta Marzec^{1,2}

¹ Fitch Laboratory, British School at Athens, 52 Souedias Street, Athens 10676, Greece

² Institute of Mediterranean and Oriental Cultures of the Polish Academy of Sciences, 72 Nowy Świat Street, Warsaw 00-330, Poland

* athena.konstandara@gmail.com

Keywords: ceramic petrography, WD-XRF, elemental analysis, Delos, Late Hellenistic, braziers, provenance, Cyclades, Eastern Mediterranean, East Aegean, trade

Delos, located in the Cyclades (Greece), was Rome’s ‘duty free’ hub in the Late Hellenistic period (166/7-89/69 BCE). The central position of the island in Mediterranean trade is reflected in the abundance and variety of ceramic materials recovered during excavations. Among them are braziers—i.e. portable cooking devices. The vast number of braziers found on the island led some scholars to assume that at least some of them were made locally. In order to test this assumption all fragments of braziers unearthed in three temples of Sarapis on Delos were examined macroscopically and 22 samples were analysed with thin section petrography and wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence. The results revealed the presence of six different fabrics, four of which are compatible with the geology of Cycladic islands located in the vicinity of Delos. All of the ‘local’ braziers have the same general morphological characteristics with subtle differences. This ‘Cycladic’ type is stylistically distinct from the ‘imported’ braziers studied, which are more compatible with East Aegean geology.

Influence of decantation on Mediterranean clay: An experimental archaeological approach

Vania Filippou^{1*}, Lara Maritan², Virginie Renson³, Daria Pasqual², Silvia Cattò², Eleni Nodarou⁴, Emma Cantisani⁵, Maria Dikomitou Eliadou⁶, Zomenia Zomeni⁷

¹ Department of Cultural Heritage: Archaeology and History of Art, Cinema and Music, Scuola di Scienze umane, sociali e del patrimonio culturale, Università degli Studi di Padova, Padua, Italy

² Department of Geosciences, University of Padova; Padua; Italy

³ University of Missouri; Columbia; MO; USA

⁴ INSTAP Study Center for East Crete; Pachia Ammos; Greece ⁵ The Institute of Heritage Science - CNR; Napoli; Italy

⁶ STARC, The Cyprus Institute; Nicosia; Cyprus ⁷ Cyprus Geological Survey; Nicosia; Cyprus

* filippouvania@yahoo.gr

Keywords: experimental, clay processing, decantation, XRF, XRPD, ICP-MS, isotopes, SEM, microscopy, petrography, Mediterranean, Atterberg Limits

Clay processing can deeply affect the characteristic of a base clay, having important effect on both provenance studies and technological issues in ceramic examinations. Decantation is one of those clay processing techniques that has been used for cleaning the clay from the impurities (coarser fraction) found in the sediment. The influence of this processing is assessed experimentally by delving into the effects it has on a mineralogical, elemental, and microscopic level. Ten clayey materials were sampled from different geographic location in the Mediterranean basin (Cyprus, Greece, Italy and Sudan) to undergo a multianalytical approach before and after they were depurated. X-ray Fluorescence and X-ray Powder Diffraction were used to interpret the mineralogical and chemical changes of the base clay underwent, as well as laser granulometry to establish the changes in terms of grain-size distribution pre and post processing (depuration for sedimentation in calm water). The samples were also fired at 400°C facilitating thin section production enabling microscopic analysis. Digital imaging analysis using the Scanning Electron Microscope with backscattered electron images was crucial for elemental understanding of the clays. Finally, Atterberg limits were measured to explored the impact of decantation on clay plasticity, giving information on changes in mineral type content and organic material. The samples are to be further tested in the close future for isotopic analysis and ICP-MS. By addressing these changes, the study aims to deepen our understanding of clay behavior, therefore helping develop our insights into ceramic production techniques and facilitating provenance studies.

Envisioning pre-colombian regional trade patterns through elemental analysis of archaeological ceramics from Western Panama

Carly Pope^{1*}, Scott Palumbo², Laure Dussubieux³

¹ University of California, Los Angeles USA

² College of Lake County, Illinois, USA

³ Elemental Analysis Facility at The Field Museum, Chicago, Illinois, USA

* c3m2pope@g.ucla.edu

Keywords: ceramic analysis, LA-ICP-MS, provenance

Gran Chiriquí, as an archaeological culture area, spans from southern Costa Rica to western Panama and crosses at least three topographic subdivisions – the Pacific Coast, Central Highlands, and the Caribbean Coast – as well as several modern political ones. Of these, the Caribbean Coast is the least studied and has been of little interest archaeologically, primarily in comparison to sites in the Pacific Coast. However, Isla Colón, the largest island in Caribbean Panama, has recently proven unique in the region: the ceramic assemblage from Sitio Drago on Isla Colón's north shore is more diverse than any known in the region and includes locally-made ceramics, imported wares, and local imitations of exotic styles. To assess the role of Isla Colón in Pre-Columbian trade networks and the ways in which its inhabitants interacted with others in Gran Chiriquí, we performed laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry on archaeological ceramic and clay samples from across Western Panama. The identification of distinct groups based on chemical composition enables us to distinguish possible differences in location of production, or provenance, and thereby establish which ceramic types were being moved and when. This delineation of networks of interaction is based on pottery samples from seven archaeological sites representing three subregions of Gran Chiriquí in the period from AD 1-1500, a period that is traditionally divided into the Aguas Buenas, San Lorenzo, and Chiriquí phases. This collaborative provenance study is pioneering as archaeometric analyses of ceramics have not been undertaken in this area previously.

μ-LIBS imaging as spatially-resolved and quantitative characterization method for pottery

Nicolas Herreyre^{1,2*}, Valérie Merle¹, Anne Schmitt¹, Christine Oberlin¹, Clothilde Comby-Zebino², Vincent Motto-Ros²

¹ ArAr, CNRS & Université Lyon 2, Lyon, France

² iLM, Université Lyon1, Villeurbanne, France

* nicolas.herreyre@univ-lyon1.fr

Keywords: pottery, ceramology, petrography, quantification, μ-LIBS imaging

In our pursuit of characterizing pottery, we are pioneering a novel approach for multi-analytical characterization through μ-LIBS imaging technique (Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy). This cutting-edge methodology facilitates surface analysis spanning a few centimeters, generating an extensive dataset of spectra, upwards of one million and beyond. LIBS offers comprehensive elemental maps with micrometric resolution, crucial for mineral characterization. Supplementing the capabilities of conventional microscopic petrography, our method enables the identification of the granular fraction, known as the temper, on a straightforward polished section of a sherd. Given the substantial volume of data produced across a large surface area, leveraging machine learning for rapid and automated spectrum processing emerges as a potent tool for recognizing mineral families within a sample. These outcomes can subsequently be harnessed to estimate temper characteristics, akin to the capabilities of quantitative microscopy. The resulting maps expedite the examination of temper proportion relative to clay, encompassing both grain size and shape distributions. Notably, in contrast to other elemental techniques providing an overall composition of a sample, such as XRF, the distinctive advantage of μ-LIBS lies in furnishing spatially-resolved spectra across the entire surface. This enables segmentation, allowing the exclusion of temper contributions from the bulk composition of a sherd. Consequently, a quantitative analysis of the clay alone becomes feasible, facilitating comparisons across different potteries irrespective of the added temper, as it is necessary for Lugdunum's production. This, in turn, holds promise for enhanced identification of raw material sources and hence the provenance of vessels in future investigations.

Fragments of the past from Zeytinli Bahçe Höyük: Deciphering cultural and technological interactions from the Late Chalcolithic to the Early Bronze Age through ceramic petrography.

Rosa Crocco^{1*}

¹ Sapienza Università di Roma, Rome, Italy

* rosa.crocco@uniroma1.it

Keywords: petrography, ceramic technology, Zeytinli Bahçe Höyük, Late Chalcolithic, Middle Euphrates

The site of Zeytinli Bahçe Höyük, located near Birecik (Urfa province, Turkey), provides a valuable testimony to the complex cultural history of the Middle Euphrates Valley over several millennia. Its strategic position and extensive stratigraphic sequence, spanning from the 4th millennium BC to the late Byzantine/medieval period, make it an excellent observatory for studying the numerous changes that have affected southeastern Anatolia and northern Mesopotamia over time. At the YRA 2024 Conference, preliminary results of petrographic analyses conducted using polarized light microscopy on a selection of ceramic artifacts from the Late Chalcolithic 3-5 levels and the Early Bronze Age I (from the early 4th millennium BC to the early 3rd millennium BC) of Zeytinli Bahçe will be presented. The collected data allow us to trace the evolution of craft practices related to the site's ceramic production, from the origin of raw materials to the manufacturing techniques of the vessels. Through this analysis, it has been possible to identify the persistence of some traditions in the manufacture and use of the vessels, as well as modifications linked to the socio-economic and cultural transformations within the communities that inhabited Zeytinli Bahçe. These data contribute to the debate on the cultural and social transformations that characterized Greater Mesopotamia in the 4th millennium BC, with a particular focus on the northward expansion of Uruk culture groups, aiming to clarify the impact and scope of external cultural influences, such as that of the Uruk culture, on local traditions.

Knowledge exchange in pottery production in Neolithic Northwest China: a petrographic study and the resulting development of a digital tool for petrographic image analysis in archaeology

Evgenia Dammer^{1*}

¹ Rathgen Research Laboratory, Prussian Cultural Heritage Foundation, Berlin, Germany

* dammer.evgenia@gmail.com

Keywords: pottery technology, petrography, research software, prehistoric pottery, shared knowledge

This paper explores the potential for long-distance knowledge sharing in the production of Majiayao-style pottery in Neolithic Northwest China through macroscopic and microscopic analyses. The paper is divided into two parts. The first part examines the chaîne opératoire of the pottery production process based on tool-trace analysis, petrography, and comparisons with experimentally fired geological samples. The striking consistency and similarities in raw material selection, construction, and firing techniques among pottery from different sites suggest mechanisms for technological knowledge exchange among Neolithic potters. Given that pottery is the most abundant or sole evidence for human activity in the region during the Neolithic, the technological perspective presented in this study proves useful in understanding social connectivity and shared knowledge. The second part presents the development of visualization software to enhance the analysis of petrographic photomicrographs in archaeological research. This idea emerged from the methodological challenges faced during the comparative studies of pottery from different sites and geological samples. Traditional thin-section petrography requires laborious visual comparison of individual samples under a microscope. Existing petrography software, primarily designed for geology, lacks features needed for archaeological research, such as multiple sample comparison. The proposed software allows for the simultaneous viewing of multiple photomicrographs, improving the efficiency of analysing ceramic pastes. Developed openly on GitHub with an OSI-approved license, this software aims to be a sustainable tool, fostering collaboration among archaeologists and software engineers, and applicable to any research involving thin-section petrography.

Mineralogical and petrographic study of tuyères from Pongsolo (Lekie, Central Cameroon)

Epossi Ntah Zoila Luz-Kroll^{1,2*}

¹ Department of Arts and Archaeology, Faculty of Arts, Letters and Social Sciences, University of Yaounde 1, Yaounde, Cameroon

² Forschungsbereich Archäometallurgie, Leibniz-Forschungsmuseum für Georessourcen/Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum, Bochum, Germany

* zoila.epossi@univ-yaounde1.cm

Keywords: tuyères, archaeometallurgy, mineralogy, petrography, firing temperature, Cameroon

Pongsolo is located in the Lekie Division of Central Cameroon. Archaeological studies have confirmed the presence of iron smelting activities at this site between the 15th and 16th century AD. Eight fragments of tuyères from Pongsolo were analysed by X-ray diffraction and polarised optical microscopy to determine their mineralogy, and deduce their firing temperature and the iron smelting temperature. Five tuyères are reddish with some black parts on their surface, whereas the three others are black and covered with a layer of slag. X-ray diffraction revealed three mineralogical groups of samples: The first group (2 samples) contained quartz, muscovite, and kaolinite. The second group (3 samples) contained muscovite and quartz and the third group (3 samples) contained mullite and quartz. The results of polarised optical microscopy agree with the mineralogical groups. The first group is characterised by a reddish matrix with an abundance of mica flakes (biotite and muscovite), indicating a firing temperature range below 600 °C due to the presence of kaolinite. The second group has a dark matrix with few mica flakes, indicating a temperature range of 600 to 900 °C. The third group is characterised by a vitrified matrix, indicating a firing temperature above 1000 °C. The variation of the mineralogy and the firing temperature of the tuyères can be explained by their different position in the furnace. The presence of mullite, vitrification, quartz and a layer of slag in the third group indicated an iron smelting temperature between 1000 and 1300°C.

The elemental composition of bog ores in Masovia (Poland) and its affect on the reconstruction of the smelting process

Antonina Bebłowska-Bednarkiewicz^{1*}

¹ Department of Archaeology, University of Warsaw, Warsaw, Poland

* a.bednarkiew@student.uw.edu.pl

Keywords: archeometallurgy, iron smelting, Przeoworsk culture, Masovian centre of metallurgy

During the period of Roman Influence (1st-3rd century AD), in Poland existed three large metallurgical centers of the Przeworsk culture: Świętokrzyskie, Silesian and Masovian. These centers were famous for their large-scale iron production. The ore was fired in clay furnaces resembling chimneys, which were filled with coal and ore in layers. In the Świętokrzyskie Mountains, experimental research reconstructing the iron smelting process has been taking place since the 1950s. Experimental research was carried out there, including physico-chemical research, to help analyze the iron smelting process at the atomic level. In Masovia, experiments focused primarily on the design aspects of the furnace chimney. This project focuses on the chemical-physical composition of bog iron ore. The ore will be tested for its elemental composition. The results will be compared with the ore found at mining sites from the 2nd century AD. The analysis will show whether there are differences in the elemental composition of the iron age and modern ore and how it affects the experimental results.

Bronze production in Archaic and Classical Northern Greece: An archaeometric approach to the study of bronze objects from Ancient Argilos

Justine Lefebvre^{1*}

¹ Université de Montréal

* justine.lefebvre@umontreal.ca

Keywords: archaeometallurgy, bronze

Argilos was founded on the littoral of the Strymonic Gulf in the mid-7th century BCE. Shortly after its foundation, the city became very prosperous, benefiting from good relations with the local Thracian populations, fertile lands, easy access to various commercial markets, and the abundant wood and metal resources the area has been famous for since Antiquity. Through a Greek-Canadian collaboration, archaeological research carried out in Argilos since 1992 has allowed the discovery of a rich material culture, amongst which are found more than a thousand bronze artifacts. The systematic study of the Argilos' bronze collection was initiated in 2017 with typological analysis. With limited conclusive results, the scope of the study has been widened by using archaeometric methods, such as metallographic, chemical, and isotopic analyses, carried out on 150 artifacts. With the use of these methods, we seek to contribute to the current state of knowledge on archaic and classical metal production in Northern Greece. Indeed, questions concerning the organization of Argilos bronze production, its integration within its regional context in terms of distribution of primary resources and finished products, and exchange of technological knowledge with other production centers will be addressed. During this presentation, results of the metallographic analysis will be studied. Through the discussion of the latter, we will argue that Argilos' bronze production was subject to a great degree of standardization, demonstrating a high level of mastery of technical metal processes. In addition, the possibility of a vast distribution network going beyond the region will be explored.

Silver-lead and copper production on Early Bronze Age southern Sifnos: an overview

Magda Giannakopoulou^{1*}

¹ Department of History and Archaeology, University of Athens, Greece

* magdakig@yahoo.com

Keywords: archaeometallurgy, smelting, cupellation, Early Bronze Age, Aegean

Metallurgy is always thought to have played a vital role in the development of the Early Bronze Age Aegean societies, being connected to economic development and social complexity. This paper is an overview of the archaeometallurgical study of remains from Early Bronze Age sites located on southern Sifnos, Skali, Kasela and Akrotiraki. The metallurgical remains, lead and copper slag, litharge and furnace wall fragments have been studied using Optical Microscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy with Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (SEM-EDX). Skali is a copper smelting site, where primary and secondary copper minerals, probably local, were smelted in non-perforated furnaces. At Kasela, the only currently known lead smelting site in the Early Bronze Age Aegean, local argentiferous lead ore was smelted within perforated furnaces. Part of the activities conducted within the settlement of Akrotiraki are related to lead-silver production. The slag from Akrotiraki derives either from smelting of argentiferous lead ore like Kasela, or a refining process of possibly the metal produced at Kasela. The litharge fragments are litharge impregnated hearth linings related to cupellation, whilst silver metal has been detected in some of the samples. Therefore, on southern Sifnos in a radius of approximately 500m the two main stages of the lead-silver production, smelting and cupellation, as well as the primary production of copper are present, rendering it the only area within the Early Bronze Age Aegean that all the above stages of metallurgical production co-exist.

TerraLID: Further steps towards a new ecosystem for lead isotope data in archaeology

Thomas Rose^{1*}

¹ Forschungsbereich Archäometallurgie, Leibniz-Forschungsmuseum für Georessourcen/Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum, Bochum, Germany

² Forschungsbereich Montanarchäologie, Leibniz-Forschungsmuseum für Georessourcen/Deutsches Bergbau-Museum Bochum, Bochum, Germany

³ Rechenzentrum, Technische Hochschule Georg Agricola, Bochum, Germany

⁴ Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Bochum, Germany

⁵ FIERCE, Frankfurt Isotope & Element Research Centre, Goethe Universität Frankfurt, Frankfurt am Main, Germany

* thomas.rose@bergbaumuseum.de

Keywords: lead isotope data, research data, database, infrastructure

Lead isotopes are currently the most powerful method for the reconstruction of the raw material provenance of non-ferrous metals. The success of the method relies crucially on the availability of reference data from all potential ore deposits or other suitable materials with a known production location. OXALID was the first open access database for such data, and many more followed since. While they are great resources, data compilation is still a tedious task because these datasets are usually published in a static format (e.g., as supporting information of articles) and the authors follow their own approaches in the description of the data. The result is datasets that are difficult to combine but to a large extent based on the same pool of publications. To overcome this situation, TerraLID builds upon the prototype GlobalID but aims to significantly enhance its functionalities towards a digital research data infrastructure that allows the publication, compilation and interpretation of lead isotope data for a large variety of archaeological and geological materials. It aims to implement the FAIR data principles in a community-driven process to ensure that the research infrastructure and metadata are developed close to the needs of the community. The TerraLID team is open, meaning that it welcomes all kinds of contributions from the community and provides many opportunities to get involved in the development process. This contribution will highlight some of these opportunities and presents examples of how this process shaped the design of TerraLID.

Metalworking materials and practices from Late Antique Rome

Giulia Bison^{1*}, Jose Cristobal Carvajal Lopez²

¹ University of Leicester

² INCIPIT-CSIC (Institute for Heritage Sciences-CSIC)

* gb276@leicester.ac.uk

Keywords: archaeometallurgy, copper alloy, technical ceramics, petrography

In recent decades, archaeological research in the monumental centre of Rome has revealed a completely new image of the city in Late Antiquity. In particular, the reoccupation of former public spaces for productive activities, among which metalworking seems to have played a prominent role, has been extensively documented. Recent excavations of three metalworking furnaces have yielded a considerable amount of material related to the secondary processing of iron and copper alloys, in particular metal debris and technical ceramics, recorded for the first time in Italy and especially in Rome. The main novelties are two nozzles from bellows at one site and numerous fragments of crucibles from two other sites, which turned out to be kitchenware items repurposed with a refractory lining, revealing an operational pattern for the production of these vessels. All these materials have been subjected to scientific analysis, the results of which, although partial, represent a novelty for the Roman scene and have provided a first, unexpected insight into the alloys and materials used, as well as some of the technological choices made by the metallurgists, showing that the subject merits further study. These studies will allow us to adventure some preliminary answers to archaeologically relevant questions about the economic and social life of Late Antique Rome. This is a very initial approach to larger questions such as the management of resources from a recycling perspective and the potential supply of raw materials.

Commercial high alumina crucibles for melting alkali and alkaline earth metal salt mixtures to replicate ancient glass production

Marcel Frenken^{1*}

¹ Science and Technology in Archaeology and Culture Research Center (STARC), The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus

* m.frenken@cyi.ac.cy

Keywords: experimental archaeology, technical ceramics, material analysis

We investigate the chemical refractoriness of high alumina (60-70 wt% Al₂O₃) crucibles rich in mullite and corundum intended for melting alkali and alkaline earth metal salts. These salts and salt mixtures produce chemically aggressive and low viscosity melts capable of dissolving quartz and crucible walls alike. These interactions are significant for understanding ancient glassmaking processes, as they were used as fluxes to lower the melting temperature of silica, thus being vital components in ancient glass making. The study evaluates the reactivity and interactions of various salts and salt mixtures with an emphasis on their effects on the crucible's structural integrity and potential seeping through ceramic porosity or even overboiling. Common salts are used to simulate ancient fluxes which were natural mixtures of sodium carbonate and sodium chloride, potassium carbonate, calcium carbonate and sulfate, among others. Various mixtures were tested under controlled laboratory conditions and the results used to outline a detailed protocol for safety precautions necessary when experimenting with these aggressive melts. This study provides a critical assessment on the advantages and disadvantages of using commercially available crucibles and salt raw materials for replicating ancient glassmaking processes. Furthermore, it lays the foundation for the understanding of the reactions between (natural) flux mixtures and the silica source (sand or powdered quartz) during plant-ash glassmaking.

The interaction between Persian Gulf and Indian Peninsular during the middle-late Islamic Period: Compositional evidence for the high-alumina glass bangles discovered from coastal sites of Qatar and U.A.E.

Qian Cheng^{1,2*}, Thilo Rehren¹, Robert Andrew Carter³, Xueyan Zhang⁴

¹ STARC, The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia, Cyprus

² Conservation department, China National Centre for Archaeology, Beijing, China

³ Qatar Museum, Doha, Qatar

⁴ Conservation Standards Research Institute, the Palace Museum, Beijing, China

* q.cheng@cyi.ac.cy

Keywords: glass bangles, high-Al glass, Persian gulf, India, Islamic period

Glass and ceramic artifacts were widely distributed along the trade routes between the East and West during significant periods of trade and cultural exchange, reflecting interactions from manufacturing regions to consuming societies. In the Persian Gulf region, a considerable quantity of ceramic sherds and glass ornaments and vessel fragments have been excavated from coastal town sites in the U.A.E. (14th-16th century CE) and Northern Qatar (18th-20th century CE). Archaeological assemblages indicate that glass bangles were a common accessory during the mid-late Islamic period. Compositional analysis of these representative glass bangles, conducted by LA-ICP-MS and SEM-EDS, revealed several bangles with high alumina content, distinguishing them from the predominant plant ash soda-lime-silica glass of the Islamic period. These unique samples were further classified into two subgroups based on their mineral and plant ash flux compositions. This study aims to identify the possible provenances of these high-Al subgroups relevant to different areas of the Indian Peninsula in terms of major and trace elements of the glasses, and also to illustrate a broad distribution landscape of high-alumina glass spanning South Asia, West Asia, the Levant, and even China. Additionally, the manufacturing techniques of polychrome bangles will be discussed in conjunction with micro-CT analysis results.

Identifying a Peloponnesian palette: pigment analysis of domestic architecture from Stymphalos

Alice Clinch^{1*}

¹ Departments of History of Art and Visual Studies & the Cornell Institute of Archaeology and Material Studies

* ac2773@cornell.edu

Keywords: pigment, plaster, pXRF, XRD

This paper presents the results of analysis of painted plaster from Stymphalos in the north east Peloponnese. Excavations at the lower town site uncovered two large elite residences, one of which had a large quantity of surviving wall plaster in moulded stucco panels. Both the three-dimensional stucco style and the faux-marble painted effect are representative of the Hellenistic Masonry style of wall plaster, which to date has only been discovered in limited quantities. In general, there have been few discoveries of Hellenistic domestic painted plaster in Greece, with the majority of material from this period belonging to funerary contexts. This research employs a multianalytical approach in the identification of materials, providing an important contribution to the understanding of pigments used in domestic decoration in the Hellenistic period.

The “production” of Minoan red serpentinite

Killian Regnier^{1,2*}

¹ FNRS Research Fellow; Institut des civilisations, arts et lettres (INCAL), UCLouvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium

² Laboratoire de géologie de Lyon: Terre, planètes, environnement (LGL-TPE), Lyon I, Lyon, France

* killian.regnier@uclouvain.be

Keywords: mineralogy, serpentinite, heating experiments, Minoan stone vessels

In the Bronze Age (Minoan) palatial site of Malia, Crete, in the so-called “Quartier Mu” of the Protopalatial period (1900-1700 BCE), were found, among particularly rich and varied artefact assemblages, c. 25 vases made of “red serpentinite”. Serpentinite is a metamorphic rock that typically ranges from grey-green to grey-blue, and its red variant, which is much rarer, has not yet been found in natural outcrops in Crete. Because of this, and the fact that its red colour is typically associated with high-temperature metamorphism, it seems that Minoan red serpentinite has not been transformed through natural geological processes but by anthropogenic heating actions. However, the exact conditions of this firing process, as well as whether it was intentional (craftsmanship) or accidental (destruction by fire in Quartier Mu), have not yet been assessed nor demonstrated. This talk aims to address these issues by examining the different potential heating conditions that lead to the modification of the colour of the stone, arguing for an intentional heating process. This will be achieved through laboratory experimental heating supported by geochemical and mineralogical analyses, and by comparisons with the archaeological material. It will additionally provide a preliminary overview of other red serpentinite artifacts found in Minoan Crete. Finally, because Quartier Mu has revealed different types of production linked in part to the elite spheres (metal, pottery and seal production), it will be proposed that the production of red serpentinite at Malia may have emerged thanks to the emulation between the various crafts taking place in the Quarter.

Trace element influence on phytolith dissolution and preservation: Investigating the role of strontium and barium

Nafsika C. Andriopoulou^{1*}

¹ Laboratory of Geophysical - Satellite Remote Sensing and Archaeoenvironment, Institute for Mediterranean Studies, Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas, 74100 Rethymnon Crete, Greece

² School of Mineral Resources Engineering, Technical University of Crete, 73133 Chania Crete, Greece

* nafsika.andriopoulou@gmail.com

Keywords: phytoliths, dissolution, strontium, barium, geoarchaeology

Several vascular plants produce silicate, calcium carbonate, and calcium oxalate phases in inorganic components of the plants known as phytoliths ($\text{SiO}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$), through biomineralisation. Additionally, smaller amounts of strontium oxalate, strontium sulphate, and barium sulphate phases, among others, have been reported in various plants. Although phytolith analysis is an internationally emerging field, recent studies on phytoliths have not emphasised the extent to which the presence of trace chemical elements affects the dissolution of biogenic silicon and, consequently, the preservation of microscopic phytoliths in geoarchaeological contexts. Toward this end, this project investigates the dissolution behaviour of phytoliths (extracted from fresh wheat cultivated in Greece and Cyprus) in relation to variations of pH, temperature, and time through long-term batch laboratory experiments. Specifically, the mobility of strontium (Sr) and barium (Ba) was studied using ICP-MS, with data processed using MATLAB software. The Sr and Ba displayed almost identical behaviour with a very rapid initial elemental release predominantly within the first five days of the leaching experiment. For the high-resolution characterisation of phytolith morphology, mineralogy, and chemistry, a variety of complementary analytical techniques were employed, including OLM, SEM/EDS, XRD, FTIR, ED-XRF, CHNS and TGA-DTGA. Strontium was detected in some EDS spectra, and strontianite (SrCO_3) and/or celestite (SrSO_4) were identified in the XRD traces. In this study, Ba-minerals were not identified in the phytoliths; the release of Ba along with Sr during the leaching experiments, suggests that Ba may participate in the crystal lattice of strontium carbonate and/or sulphate mineral, substituting for Sr.

Deciphering past coastal environments: Beachrock characterisation and Luminescence Dating in SE Lasithi, Crete, Greece

Nafsika C. Andriopoulou^{1*}

¹ Laboratory of Geophysical - Satellite Remote Sensing and Archaeoenvironment, Institute for Mediterranean Studies, Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas, 74100 Rethymnon Crete, Greece

² Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, National Centre for Scientific Research "Demokritos", 15341 Athens, Greece

³ Department of Physics - Archaeometry Center, University of Ioannina, 45110 Ioannina, Greece

⁴ X-ray Center, Technische Universität Wien, Getreidemarkt 9, 1060 Vienna, Austria

⁵ School of Mineral Resources Engineering, Technical University of Crete, 73133 Chania Crete, Greece

⁶ Biology Department, University of Crete, 70013 Heraklion Crete, Greece

* nafsika.andriopoulou@gmail.com

Keywords: beachrock, optically stimulated luminescence, archaeological science, coastal (archaeo)environments

The study assesses the palaeoenvironmental significance of coastal and shallow submarine deposits through the detailed characterisation and absolute dating of beachrock. The physicochemical composition of beachrock deposits provides valuable insights into the sediment types present during beachrock formation over time. The dating technique used was optically stimulated luminescence (OSL). Established analytical techniques, including X-ray powder diffraction (XRD), wavelength-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (WD-XRF), and scanning electron microscopy with energy-dispersive spectroscopy (SEM/EDS), were employed for rigorous characterisation of the morphology, as well as qualitative and quantitative mineralogical and elemental composition of the selected samples. Beachrock mapping and sampling were conducted at selected sites along the c.a. 20-km length coastal front of Southeastern Lasithi, Crete, Greece, specifically at Gra Lygia, Ierapetra, Koutsounari, and Ferma sites. The comprehensive characterisation and dating of the samples contributed to refining the chronological context of the beachrock phases in the studied areas (partially presented in previous studies) and facilitated a re-examination of the (micro)environmental conditions, such as the processes involved in beachrock formation and regional trends in past sea level dynamics during the Upper Holocene. Consequently, this first in-depth integrated

approach to this area will provide insights into the environmental processes shaping the broader archaeological landscape and illuminate the dynamic interactions between human societies and coastal environments.

A look upon Chalcolithic pottery technology through the petrographic analysis of a batch from north of Danube

Mădălina Dimache^{1,2*}, Cristian-Eduard Ștefan³

¹ National History Museum of Romania, Calea Victoriei, No. 12, Bucharest, Romania

² University of Bucharest

³ Vasile Pârvan Institute of Archeology, Henri Coandă street, No 11, Bucharest, Romania

* dimachemadalina@gmail.com

Keywords: North of Danube, Chalcolithic, pottery, petrography

The current paper aims to present and discuss the main results obtained from the study of ceramic fragments analyzed by polarized light optical microscope in the collection of the Vasile Pârvan Institute of Archaeology, Bucharest, from a petrographic point of view. They come from Chalcolithic period vessels discovered in three settlements from Romania, Bârlălești-Stanția (Vaslui County), Aldeni-Gurguiul Balaurului (Buzău County) and Bălănești-Muceha Mare (Buzău County), all three belonging to the Stoicani-Aldeni cultural aspect. The Stoicani-Aldeni aspect was defined as a “mixed aspect” or “synthesis facies” between the Gumelnița and the Pre-Cucuteni/Cucuteni civilizations, initially on the basis of archaeological excavations at Stoicani-Cetățuia (south-east Romania, Galați County) and Aldeni- Gurguiul Balaurului. This presentation will discuss the results obtained on a batch of Chalcolithic pottery from Eastern and South-East of Romania (ca. 4600-4000 cal BC). Ceramic fragments come from vessels that are typologically different such as bowls, pots, cups, cup, storage vessels and a tray. Following the petrographic analysis, some differences were observed in terms of textural, microstructure, porosity and even compositional characteristics.

Furthering our understanding of the sources of the metal of Roman denarii: A multi-isotope and elemental analysis approach

Tim Greifelt^{1*}

¹ Forschungsbereich Archäometallurgie, Deutsches Bergbau-Museum, Bochum, Germany

² Institut für Archäologische Wissenschaften, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Bochum, Germany

³ Römisch-Germanische Kommission des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts, Frankfurt am Main, Germany

* Tim.Greifelt@bergbaumuseum.de

Keywords: Roman denarius, lead isotopes, copper isotopes, provenance

Since coins are generally an officially produced medium, provenance studies of the metal used to produce them can provide important information on the logistical, infrastructural and organizational capacities of central authorities. Thus, it is not surprising that ancient coins have been the subject of a large number of archaeometallurgical studies, in particular involving lead isotopes. The composition of the silver in the coin metal of Roman Imperial denarii has been intensively investigated in recent years by Kevin Butcher and Matthew Ponting. However, the work concentrated primarily on the chemical composition, with a relatively smaller number of isotopic analyses being carried out, and concentrating on specific questions. To complement the investigations of Butcher and Ponting, more than 200 coins from the period 30 BC to AD 240 have been sampled for isotopic analysis in a project based at the German Mining Museum in Bochum. Besides standard lead isotopes, these analyses also included copper and silver isotopes, which were performed in Bochum, at the Frankfurt Isotope and Element Research Center FIERCE, the Laboratoire de Géologie de Lyon, École normale supérieure de Lyon, and in the Institute for Geosciences at the Goethe University Frankfurt. The combination of isotopic analyses of different elements has provided deeper, sometimes surprising insights, qualifying the information provided by lead isotopes alone. This paper will present the first results and interpretation of our analyses, so indicating how a combination of isotopic methods can advance our understanding of the provenance and the methods used to obtain the raw materials.

An application of XRF spectroscopy to heritage science: the case study of ancient Roman building materials from Lebanon

Marcin Sokołowski^{1*}

¹ Faculty of Archaeology & Faculty of Physics, University of Warsaw, Warsaw, Poland

* m.sokolowsk6@student.uw.edu.pl

Keywords: XRF, hierarchical clustering, building materials

The talk will explore the application of X-ray fluorescence analysis to the investigation of archaeological samples of plaster and mortar from the ancient Roman villages of Chhim and Jiyeh, Lebanon. The topic of statistical analysis of results (based on PCA and hierarchical analysis) and their interpretation will be discussed, i.e., how to translate differences in the chemical composition of plaster and mortar samples into dating architectural monuments, determining the origin of building materials, and shedding light on how ancient builders approached their work.

Experimental clay processing and archaeometric analysis to determine the provenance of fine-ware ceramics from the Early Middle Ages in north-western Tuscany (Italy): preliminary results

Irene Strufaldi^{1*}, Sara Longo²

¹ Department of Philology, Literature and Linguistics, University of Pisa, Pisa, Italy

² Dipartimento di Scienze Matematiche, Fisiche e Naturali, University of Florence, Florence, Italy

* irene.strufaldi@gmail.com

Keywords: ceramic petrography, comparative catalogue, clay processing, experimental archaeology, Early Middle Ages

The goal of this research is to create a comparative catalogue of raw materials and clays from the northern Tuscany region (Italy) used in fine wares, which will serve as a reference database for determining the provenance of archaeological fine wares. Coarse-ware ceramics are generally easier to trace back to their place of origin compared to fine wares, as the latter contain less petrographic information. To address this challenge, a systematic clay sampling campaign was conducted, collecting samples from outcrops near well-known production centers in the north-western Tuscany. This paper presents the clay processing workflow and preliminary results from XRF and XRD analyses of the raw materials. A multi-analytical approach will be further adopted, involving the study of experimental briquettes fired at various temperature ranges using optical microscopy (OM) to complement the minero-petrographic analysis. Additionally, cathodoluminescence on thin sections will be performed at the Archéosciences Laboratory of the University of Bordeaux Montaigne. This catalogue is part of a broader project aimed at reconstructing the sets of vessels used between the 7th and 10th centuries AD in north Tuscany, as well as understanding the trading dynamics of that period. Determining the provenance and distribution of these ceramics is crucial, as the movement of archaeological ceramics from their production centers to their find spots is related to various human activities such as trade, exchange, and mobility. Therefore, identifying the origins of both coarse-wares and fine-wares can provide significant insights into historical trade patterns.

The RETS Project: Revealing the Senne. A hidden landmark in the historical center of Brussels, Belgium

Dries Vergouwen^{1*}

¹ Archaeology, Environmental Changes & Geo-Chemistry, Free University of Brussels (VUB), Brussels, Belgium

² urban.brussels, Brussels, Belgium

³ AMGC, VUB, Brussels, Belgium

* Dries.Vergouwen@vub.be

Keywords: geoarchaeology, river reconstruction, (palaeo)environment

Throughout history, the Senne river has always been an important landmark for Brussels. In the past, the river served multiple functions. It was essential for providing food and water, for waste disposal, navigation and transport. Infrastructures such as mills, breweries, fortifications and fishponds could be found along its banks. The course of the river Senne and its side branches has changed drastically across history. As the landscape and the city developed, the river's flow was adapted in natural and artificial ways. Today, many questions remain unanswered concerning the evolution of the Senneriver valley, and the general human-environment interactions across history. Recent (geo)archaeological research conducted under the auspices of urban.brussels, the Brussels Regional Administration in charge of the archaeological heritage, has shown the tremendous archaeological potential of the river valley to reach a renewed understanding of the development of the Senne and its branches. Therefore, the RETS project aims to provide a synthesis of the archaeological, environmental and historical data from the Senne valley within the historical center of Brussels, starting from the Holocene until the 19th century. The research will generate maps and 3D-models which will be integrated in the publicly accessible regional cartographic platform BruGIS. These newly developed tools will as such contribute to an optimal management of the archaeological heritage in the research area.